

Exploring Tribal Communities: Insights from Manipur and Neighbouring States

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This paper critically analyses the Scheduled Tribes (ST) community in Manipur, contextualized within the broader framework of ST issues in India. The recognition of STs in India emerged in 1950, addressing centuries of historical prejudice, socioeconomic exploitation, and isolation. The Indian Constitution categorizes the population into five groups, with the ST category in Manipur being one of them. In Manipur, tribals face economic, social, and political disadvantages, prompting their listing as ST under Part X of the Constitutional ST Order, 1950. This article examines the characteristics of STs in India and Manipur, including geographical isolation, unique culture, and primordial characteristics. It also explores the cultural and traditional practices of various ethnic groups in Manipur, including the Meitei, Kukis, and Nagas. The paper analyses the Indian Constitution's ST Order and amendments about Manipur and neighboring states, focusing on the 'Kuki or Any Kuki' and 'Any Naga Tribes.' By examining the implications of ST designations, this research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex issues surrounding STs in India and Manipur.

Keywords: manipur, scheduled tribes, population, kuki, naga, constitutional order, amendments, any-kuki tribes

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1. Introduction

Located in northeastern India, Manipur characterized itself as a unique geography, with fertile valleys surrounded by mountains and hills. The state's history as a princely state has contributed to the distinct cultural identities of its inhabitants. Manipur has diverse ethnic groups, including the Meiteis, Kukis, and Nagas, each with their language, customs, and traditions. Geographically, Manipur comprises hill and valley areas, with the hills comprising approximately 90% of the state's total area. The population is similarly divided, with the valley areas inhabited predominantly by Meiteis, while the hills are home to Kukis, Nagas, and other tribal communities. According to the Constitution (Scheduled Tribes), Order, 1950, 33 tribes are recognized as Scheduled Tribes (ST) in Manipur. However, the categorization of STs in the state has undergone significant changes over the years, with the deletion and re-inclusion of certain tribes. This article aims to explore the complexities of ST designations in Manipur, focusing on the Kuki and Naga tribes, and examine the implications of these designations on the social, economic, and political lives of tribal communities in the state.

2. Objectives of the Study

(i) Constitutional Analysis: Examine the Constitution ST Order and Amendment by the Indian Government relating to the ST in Manipur. This objective focuses on understanding the legal framework governing STs in Manipur.

(ii) Demographic Analysis: Identify and analyze the Kukis and Nagas tribes or ST and their population and literacy rate as per the 2011 census in Manipur. This objective aims to provide a demographic overview of the ST population in Manipur, focusing on the Kukis and Nagas.

(iii) Comparative Analysis: Examine Any Kukis and Any Nagas tribes in Manipur with neighboring states as per the Indian Constitutional ST Order. This objective compares Manipur's ST designations and characteristics with those in neighboring states.

3. Significance of the Study

This study examines the evolution of Scheduled Tribes (ST) in India, focusing on Manipur. The 1950 Constitutional ST Order and subsequent amendments have dynamically shaped ST category,

with deletions, re-enlistments, and additions of new ST, SC, OBC, and EWS. The significance of this study lies in its ability to identify deleted, re-enlisted, and newly added STs in India, particularly in Manipur and neighboring states. This research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the ST category, shedding light on the complexities of tribal identity and classification. Furthermore, this study highlights the importance of special recognition and protection of ST in promoting equality, justice, and social inclusion in a democratic India. The ST status provides tribals access to tangible benefits such as political representation, reserved seats in educational institutions, and government jobs. By examining the implications of ST status, this research aims to inform policymakers, stakeholders, and tribal communities about the effectiveness of existing policies and programs.

4. Statement of the Problem

The Scheduled Tribes (ST) in India, particularly in Manipur, face complex issues regarding their designation, recognition, and empowerment. Despite the Constitutional ST Order of 1950 and subsequent amendments, the ST category in Manipur has undergone significant changes, including deletions, re-enlistments, and additions of new tribes. As a result, confusion has arisen, inconsistencies, and disparities in the implementation of policies and programs aimed at promoting the welfare of ST communities. Furthermore, the lack of clarity on the definition and characteristics of tribes in India has led to difficulties in identifying and addressing the unique needs and challenges of ST populations. This study aims to fill in these gaps by investigating the development of ST designations in Manipur, analyzing the implications of ST status on tribal communities, and highlighting the significance of special recognition and protection of ST in promoting equality, justice, and social inclusion.

5. Methodology of Research

This study examines the Scheduled Tribes (ST) in Manipur using a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative and qualitative techniques.

Quantitative Analysis: The quantitative component of the study involves analyzing secondary data from (i) Census reports (2011) and (ii) the Demographic status of the ST population.

Researchers use descriptive statistics and demographic analysis to examine the population characteristics, literacy rates, and other relevant indicators of STs in Manipur.

Qualitative Methods: The qualitative component involves a comprehensive review of (i) Official government documents: Indian Gazette 1950 Constitution ST Order, Constitution ST (States Order, 1951 Parts C), and ST Constitutional Amendment Acts (1956, 2002, 2019, and 2022) (ii) Published journal articles and research papers (iii) Books and book chapters (iv) Newspapers and online news articles (v) Websites and online databases.

Thematic analysis will identify patterns and themes related to the ST category in Manipur, including constitutional provisions, policy implications, and social and economic indicators. By integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies, this study aims to present a thorough understanding of the ST category in Manipur.

1. Demographic Overview of Scheduled Tribes in Manipur

Manipur, a multi-ethnic state in India's far eastern region, boasts a diverse population. According to the 2011 India Census, the state's population is 28 55,794, across 22,327 square kilometers (Ministry of Tribal Affairs, 2022). The population comprises the valley and hill regions, with 58.9% residing in the valleys and 41.1% in the hills. The hill areas are predominantly inhabited by tribal communities, totaling 11 67,422 individuals. Manipur is home to 33 recognized Scheduled Tribes (ST), primarily comprising Kuki and Naga tribes, the two leading conglomerates of Manipur's tribal population. These groups are distinct and characterized by unique accents, attire, customs, and traditions. The Kuki and Naga tribes have distinct languages, cultural practices, and historical backgrounds, shaping their identities and experiences. The demographic characteristics of the ST population in Manipur are significant, with varying literacy rates, population densities, and socioeconomic indicators across different districts (A Glimpse of the Indigenous Tribes of Manipur, 2000). The following table presents the total population of ST and literacy rates for each district in Manipur, based on the 2011 Census report:

Table 1: Manipur Census (2011). ST District Wise Percentage of Population and Literacy Rate

State/District	ST Population	Overall Literacy Rate	ST Literacy Rate
State - Manipur	33%	69%	67%
Bishnupur District	1%	67%	67%
Chandel District	89%	63%	61%
Churachandpur District	94%	74%	71%
Imphal East District	6%	72%	77%
Imphal West District	5%	77%	80%
Senapati District	44%	65%	64%
Tamenglong District	96%	61%	60%
Thoubal District	0%	64%	75%
Ukhrul District	95%	72%	70%

(Ahuja, S, 2014a)

Table 2: Tribes wise in number of ST Population as per Census 2011 in Manipur

	Tribes	Population 2011		Tribes	Population 2011
SN	All ST	1, 167, 422	SN	-	-
1	Montana	2,427	18	Aimol	3, 190
2	Moyon	2, 516	19	Anal	23, 509
3	Paite	55, 542	20	Angami	95
4	Purum	278	21	Chiru	8, 599
5	Ralte	17	22	Chothe	3, 585
6	Sema	40	23	Gangte	17, 178
7	Site	6, 728	24	Hmar	48, 375
8	Suite	804	25	Kabui	103, 908
9	Tangkhul	178, 568	26	Kacha Naga	66, 158
10	Thadou	215, 913	27	Koirao	4, 475
11	Vaiphei	42, 957	28	Koireng	1, 873
12	Zou	24, 294	29	Kom	14, 528
13	Poumai Naga	127, 381	30	Lamgang	7, 770
14	Tara	1, 066	31	Mao	93, 343
15	Kharam	1, 145	32	Maram	27, 524
16	Any Kuki Tribes	28, 342	33	Maring	26, 424
17	Generic Tribes	20, 806	34	Any Mizo Tribes	8, 064

(Manipur Population Census, 2011)

According to Table 2, which presents data on the 33/34 recognized tribes in Manipur under the Constitution of India, the Thadou (Kuki) tribe is the largest Scheduled Tribe (ST) group, with a population of 215,913 individuals. The Tangkhul tribe is the second largest, with a population of 178,568. The distribution of ST populations across districts in Manipur varies significantly.

The district with the most significant percentage of STs is Tamenglong, at 96%, followed by Churachandpur district, which has a proportion of 94%. In contrast, the district with the lowest percentage of STs is Thoubal, at 0.43%. Literacy rates among STs in Manipur also exhibit variations across districts. The overall literacy rate in Manipur is 69%, whereas the 2011 Census report states that 67% of ST people are literate. Imphal West district has the highest literacy rate among STs, at 77%, followed by Thoubal district, at 75%, and Churachandpur district, at 71%. Conversely, Tamenglong district has the lowest literacy rate among STs, at 60%. These demographic characteristics highlight the diversity and complexity of ST populations in Manipur, underscoring the need for targeted policies and interventions to address their unique challenges and opportunities (Ahuja, S, 2014b).

ST (Scheduled Tribes) in the Indian Context

The term "tribe" is employed administratively in India, lacking a definitive explanation. The British colonial administration historically categorized them as "backward classes" until March 31, 1937. The 1935 Government of India Act initially designated certain groups as tribes, a classification that continued after India gained independence. Anthropologists define a tribe as a distinct cultural entity characterized by shared attributes such as language and the absence of a formal political hierarchy. However, the Indian Constitution does not define "tribal." Article 366, Clause (25) of the Indian Constitution states that "Scheduled Tribes" refers to those tribes or tribal communities, or parts thereof, considered eligible to be Scheduled Tribes under Article 342. Essentially, "Scheduled Tribes" denotes Indigenous peoples recognized by national law. While tribal groups exhibit generic similarities, they also possess distinct cultural identities. Common characteristics among tribal communities include:

- (i) Geographical isolation
- (ii) Communal lifestyle in harmony with nature
- (iii) Unique cultures, customs, traditions, and beliefs that is straightforward and non-acquisitive

These characteristics have been employed for decades to identify and categorize groups as Scheduled Tribes. The Indian Ministry of Tribal Affairs has described Scheduled Tribes as possessing primordial characteristics, a distinct culture, geographical isolation, reluctance to engage with outsiders, and socioeconomic backwardness.

However, in contemporary discourse, terms like "primitive qualities" and "backwardness" carry negative connotations and warrant revision.

2. Tribals in Manipur: An Indian Context

The tribals of Manipur were designated as Scheduled Tribes (ST) under the 1950 Indian Constitutional Order. These communities face significant economic, social, and political disadvantages, prompting their inclusion as ST under Part X of the Constitutional ST Order, 1950. The characteristics of STs in India, as defined by the Indian Constitution, apply equally to Manipur's tribals. According to the Indian Constitution, tribals in Manipur are individuals who reside in villages and rely on forests for their livelihood. They engage in shifting cultivation, locally known as *jhum*, using rudimentary tools for plowing and harvesting. Traditionally, land ownership is communal, although private land ownership has recently become more prevalent.

Manipur has several distinct tribes, predominantly inhabiting the state's hill regions. These tribes are unique to the state and comprise 33 Mongoloid Tibetan-Burmese ethnic groups. Each tribe displays prominent traits in its distinct language, culture, traditional attire, dietary habits, religion, and superstitions. The state's population can fall into distinct categories in three main ethnic groups: the Meiteis, primarily inhabit the valley regions; the Kukis; and the Nagas, who reside in the highlands. The Indian Constitution recognizes the Kukis or Any Kuki Tribes and Nagas as ST, while anthropologists classify them as Mongoloid Tibetan-Burman language speakers. Despite their distinctiveness, similarities exist between the cultural and traditional practices of these ethnic groups—the recognition of these tribes as ST is rooted in the 1950 Constitution ST Order.

3. Recognition of Kukis and Nagas under the 1950 Constitution ST Order:

The 1950 Constitution ST Order gave the President of India the authority to issue the first ST lists under Article 342 of the Indian Constitution. This Order came into effect after consultation with state governors and Rajpramukhs. The Order specifies that the tribes or tribal communities, or parts or groups within them, are ST in the states to which those Parts apply, as long as they are residents to which those Parts apply, as long as they are residents of the Schedule to this Order's sections 1 through XXII.

This Order refers to states, districts, and other territorial divisions as they existed on May 1, 1976 (Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes Orders (Amendment) Act, 1976). Section 111 of the Constitution (ST) Order, 1950—Rules and Orders—is presented in the table:

Table 3: Manipur - Part X

SN	Name of the Tribes	SN	Name of the Tribes	SN	Name of the Tribes
1	Aimol	12	Purum	23	Kom
2	Anal	13	Kacha Naga Lamgang	24	Site
3	Angami	14	Mao	25	Suite
4	Chiru	15	Maram	26	Tangkhum
5	Chothe	16	Maring	27	Thadou
6	Gangte	17	Ralte	28	Vaiphei
7	Hmar	18	Montana	29	Zou
8	Kabui (Inpui)	19	Poumei Naga	30	Moyon
9	Linking	20	Paite	31	Tarao
10	Koirao	21	Any Kuki Tribes	32	Kharam
11	Koireng	22	Any Mizo (Lushai) Tribes	33	Sema

(The Constitution Schedule Tribes Order, 1950a)

According to Table 3, Manipur is home to 33 recognized tribes, commonly called the Kuki-Chin-Mizo and Naga tribes. The Kuki-Chin-Mizo group comprises 25 of the 33 tribes. Despite their tribal affiliations, the official language of Manipur, Meitei or Manipuri, serves as a lingua franca for communication across tribes. However, each tribe has its distinct dialect. Anthropologically, all ethnic groups in Manipur are Mongoloid, sharing cultural and traditional traits despite their socio-political and linguistic variations. The Kuki-Chin-Mizo people, in particular, are known by different names in various regions. In Myanmar's Chin-Hills, they are referred to as "Chin" (Khyan in Burmese), while in Manipur and Assam, they are known as "Kuki," and in Mizoram's Lushai Hills, they are called "Lushai" or "Mizo." Researchers now commonly refer to this group as the "Zo" people based on historical, anthropological, and linguistic connections. The Thadou Kuki tribe is the largest Kuki-Chin-Mizo tribe in Manipur (Kuki Tribes, 2022).

In contrast, the Naga tribes comprise eight distinct tribes, including the Zeliangrong (consisting of three related tribes: Rongmei or Kabui, Liangmei or Poumai, and Zemei or Kacha Nagas), Tangkhul, Mao, Maram, Maring, and Tarao.

Among the Naga tribes, the Tangkhul is the second largest, accounting for 5.01% of the population in the 1981 census and 19.7% of the state's total ST population in the 2011 census (People of Manipur, 2002). The Tangkhul people inhabit eight territorial regions in the Ukhrul district and speak distinct languages and dialects. Since the arrival of the first Christian missionary in Manipur in 1896, the Ukhrul village has been a dominant force among the Tangkhuls, with their vernacular serving as a common language. The Tangkhuls are also considered the most educated tribe in Manipur. The Poumai Naga tribe, the third largest tribe in 2011, was previously counted alongside the Mao tribe in the 1991 and 2001 censuses (Kapesa, A, 2007).

4. The Constitutional Framework for Scheduled Tribes in Manipur

Manipur's population comprises three primary communities: Meiteis (General, OBC, and SC), Nagas (ST), and Kukis (ST). In Independent India, the categorization of these communities, emphasizing their shared ethnicity and identity, was reflected in the 1951 Constitutional ST listings for Manipur, where the Kuki community appears on the list as "Kuki" or "Any Kuki Tribes." The MLJ (Ministry of Law and Justice), New Delhi, published the India Extraordinary Gazette, Section I-Part II, on January 8, 2003, and the Manipur Extraordinary Gazette, Published by Authority, Government of Manipur Secretariat, Notification, Imphal, on April 14, 2003, both titled "Any Kuki Tribes" (Constitution Schedule Tribes Part C Stats Order, 1951a). As of 1951, the six North Eastern Indian provinces of Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Tripura, Nagaland, and Manipur appear in the records in the Constitution ST Order of the Government of India. Across these states, the numerous Kuki clans are called "Any Kuki Tribes" or simply "Kuki." Similarly, the Naga tribes fall under the Constitution ST Order, 1950, Part I, in the Assam Autonomous District and other tribal areas (Constitution Scheduled Tribes Order, 1950b). Amendments to the Constitution ST Order, 1950, were made in 1956, which affected Parts X and XVIII. Specifically, the amendments substituted new entries for Manipur in Part X, including:

- (i) Entry 8: "Kabui, Inpui, Rongmei;"
- (ii) Entry 9: "Kacha Naga, Liangmai, Zeme;"
- (iii) for entry 10, substitute "10 - Koirao, Thangal."

The 1951 Constitution ST (Part C States) Order stipulates that any Naga tribe is considered a Scheduled Tribe in Manipur. This classification remains in effect in the 1991 Indian Census, which listed 17 Naga tribes in Nagaland, 15 in Manipur, and 3 in Arunachal Pradesh (Constitution Schedule Tribe Part-C Stats Order, 1951b).

5. SC and ST Orders (Amendment) Act, 1956 (Act No. 63 of 1956)

The SC and ST Orders (Amendment) Act, 1956 (Act No. 63 of 1956) came into law to define Scheduled Tribes in various states and union territories following the linguistic reorganization of states. This Act added and removed tribes and castes from the SC and ST lists, providing a revised framework for classifying Scheduled Tribes in India. The Schedule to the Constitution (STs) Order, 1950, was amended by the SC and ST Orders (Amendment) Act, 1956 (Act No. 63 of 1956), which modified the list of Scheduled Tribes in Manipur. The SC and ST Orders (Amendment) Act, 1956 (Act No. 63 of 1956) came into effect by the Parliament in the first seven years of the Indian Republic. The Schedule to the Constitution (STs) Order, 1950, was changed by the means and to the extent set out in Schedule 111 (2). The SCs and STs Orders (Act 63) (Amendment) Schedule to the 1951 Constitution ST (Part C States) Order received amendments as described therein (Scheduled Caste and Schedule Tribes Amendment Act, 1956a). The Amendment Act of 1956 comes into review in the table below:

Table 4: Amendment Act 1956 for Part VI-Manipur

1	Aimol	11	Kom	21	Sema
2	Anal	12	Lamgang	22	Simte
3	Angami	13	Mao	23	Suhte/Sahte
4	Chiru	14	Maram	24	Tangkhum
5	Chothe	15	Maring	25	Thadou
6	Gangte	16	Any Mizo (Lushai) Tribes	26	Vaiphei
7	Hmar	17	Monsang	27	Zou
8	Kabui	18	Moyon	28	Koireng
9	Paite	19	Kacha Naga	29	Ralte
10	Koirao	20	Purum		-

(Schedule Caste and ST Amendment Act, 1956b)

Manipur, a state in India's northeastern region, is home to 29 tribes, as recognized by the Amendment Act of 1956 for Part VI. However, four tribes - Pomei, Tarao, Kharam, and Any Kuki Tribe -

were deleted from the 1956 Constitutional Amendment despite being recognized in the ST Constitutional Orders of 1950 and 1951. The SC and ST List 1956 Modification Order, Schedule, Part X - Manipur, acknowledges clans as "tribes," which has exacerbated the identity dilemma faced by the Kuki people due to international boundaries (Dougel, J, 2019). The 1956 Constitution SC and ST Lists Modification Order recognized a sub-clan, Thadou, to reflect related sub-clans that speak the same dialect. The term "Any Kuki Tribes" has raised questions about its effectiveness in capturing the intricate details of Kuki identity. Numerous genealogy-origin narratives constitute the essential oddity in this context. In the four or five North East Indian states, including Manipur, "Any Kuki Tribes" or "Kuki" refers to the Kuki clans.

The 1951 Constitution ST Order (Part C States), the Schedule, Manipur - Part XVI, was replaced by the 1956 Constitution SC and ST List (Modification) Order, the Schedule, Manipur-Part X. Unlike earlier Schedules, this one recognized each Kuki clan as a tribe, creating considerable internal division. In 2002, another SC and ST amending act underwent an amendment introducing further changes to the classification of Scheduled Tribes in Manipur. The following amendments are listed below:

Table 5: Amendment Act, No.10 of 2003, Manipur SC/ST Tribes 2002 Orders

	Part X - Manipur (Second Schedule, part II)	(b) Sl. No. 31 - Tarao
(i)	For entry 28, substitute 28. Vaiphei	(c) Sl. No. 32 - Kharam
(ii)	After entry 29, insert -	(d) Sl. No. 33 - Any Kuki Tribes
	(a) Sl. No.30 - Pomei Naga	-

(Scheduled Castes & Scheduled Tribes Amendment Act, 2002)

The India Extraordinary Gazette, Section (I)—Part II, published on January 8, 2003, in New Delhi, introduced a significant change to the classification of Scheduled Tribes in Manipur. Specifically, Part X—Manipur, "Any Kuki Tribes," replaced the division that had been in place for over 50 years. This Gazette reinstated the Kukis' existence in Manipur, bringing their status and recognition to other Northeastern states (Constitution Schedule Tribe's Part-C Stats Order, 1951c). The SC and ST Orders 2002 (Amendment) Act, No. 10 of 2003, introduced several key amendments.

These included the inclusion of certain tribes or tribal communities, the use of equivalent names, the removal of area limits, the splitting and clubbing of entries, and the application of area restrictions for specific tribes and castes from the list of tribes and castes in Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Manipur, Uttar Pradesh, and other states. Parts X (J) - Manipur incorporated the following amendments: (i) After entry 28, insert "28 Vaiphei;" (ii) After entry 29, add "Naga Poumai 30, Tarao 31, Kharam 32, and Any Kuki tribes, 33" (Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes Amendment Act, 2003)

The President of India is empowered to designate tribal communities, portions of tribal communities, or sections classified as ST in a state or union territory. Parliament may also add or remove any tribal community or any tribe, or segment of a tribe or part of tribal groups, from the list of ST in a notification given under paragraph (1) by law. Any future notice shall not alter this notification. The Kuki people are not only recognized in Manipur as Any Kuki Tribe but also extent in the neighboring states, including Meghalaya, Assam, Mizoram, and Tripura. The Constitution ST Order, 1950, categorized them under the generic nomenclature "Any Kuki Tribes," although Tripura listed "Kuki."

6. Any-Kuki from Neighbouring States

In Meghalaya, the Kukis reside in the Khasi-Jaintia Hills and Mizoram's Lushai Hills districts. In Tripura, they are known by various names. In Assam, they live in Karbi Anglong, Dima Hasao, Kachar, and other parts of the country (T Haokip, George, 2017). This widespread recognition of the Kuki people highlights their significance in the region. The recognized list below includes Scheduled Tribes of Any Kukis tribes in Assam, Tripura, Mizoram, and Meghalaya:

Table 6: Assam (Part II) Any Kuki Tribes in Assam 1950, including:

1	Bitrate	10	Changsan	19	Biete	28	Chongloi
2	Guite	11	Gamalhou	20	Haolai	29	Dougel
3	Mangjel	12	Harangkawl	21	Hongsung	30	Hengna
4	Kuki	13	Haokip, Haupit	22	Gangte	31	Lupheng
5	Kipgen	14	Rangkhol	23	Hanneng	32	Lhangum
6	Hajong	15	Lhouvum	24	Singson	33	Lhoujem
7	Selam	16	Sairhem	25	Vaiphei	34	Sitlhou
8	Uibuh	17	Lenthang	26	Rating	35	Kholhou
9	Misao	18	Thangngeu	27	Sukte	36	Thado &
						37	Jongbe

(Kumar, T. A., & Madhusoodan, T, 2012a)

Table 7: Meghalaya (Part XI) Any Kuki Tribes 1950, including:

1	Khelma	10	Thangngeu	19	Khollou	28	Selnam
2	Changsan	11	Honsung	20	Kipgen	29	Singson
3	Chongloi	12	Hrangkawl	21	Kuki	30	Sitlhou
4	Dougel	13	Khawchung	22	Lhoujem	31	Sukte
5	Gamalhou	14	Khawathilang	23	Lhouvum	32	Thado
6	Gangte	15	Haokip, Haupit	24	Lupheng	33	Haolai
7	Guite	16	Biate, Biete	25	Mangjel	34	Uibuh
8	Hanneng	17	Lenthang	26	Misao	35	Vaiphei
9	Jongbe	18	Lhangum	27	Riang	36	Hengna
						37	Sairhem

(Kumar, T. A., & Tripathi Madhusoodan, 2012b)

Table 8: Mizoram (Part XVII) Any Kuki tribes 1950, including:

1	Khelma	10	Thangngeu	19	Khollou	28	Selam
2	Changsan	11	Honsungh	20	Kipgen	29	Singson
3	Chongloi	12	Hrangkawl	21	Kuki	30	Sitlhou
4	Dougel	13	Khawchung	22	Lhoujem	31	Sukte
5	Gamalhou	14	Khawathlang	23	Lhouvum	32	Thado
6	Gangte	15	Haokip, Haupit	24	Lupheng	33	Haolai
7	Guite	16	Biate, Biete	25	Mangjel	34	Uibuh
8	Hanneng	17	Lenthang	26	Misao	35	Vaiphei
9	Jongbe	18	Lhangum, Mara	27	Sairhem	36	Hengna
						37	Riang

(Kumar, T. A., & Tripathi Madhusoodan, 2012c)

Table 9: Tripura (Part XV) Kuki tribes 1950:

1	Balte	5	Hajango	9	Kuntei	13	Namte
2	Belalhut	6	Rangkhole	10	Laifang	14	Paitu, Paite
3	Chhalya	7	Khareng	11	Lentei	15	Rangchan
4	Fun	8	Khephong	12	Mizel	16	Jangtei
						17	Thangluya

(Kumar, T. A. & Tripathi Madhusoodan, 2012d)

The President of India issued the 1950 Constitution ST Order by Article 342, which empowered the President to specify the Scheduled Tribes (ST) in various states. The ST 1950 Order listed 37 clans or sub-tribes as Any Kuki Tribes in three states - Schedule Part II for Assam, Schedule Part XI for Meghalaya and Schedule Part XVII for Mizoram. According to the aforementioned Presidential Orders, the government officially recognized the Kuki Tribe as a Scheduled Tribe, and there are up to 37 distinct sub-tribes within it, located in three different states. In addition, Tripura has 16 sub-tribes, collectively referred to as Kuki.

It is worth noting that there are several Kuki Tribes, including the 'Thadou' Tribe, one of the Kuki Tribes. The Thadou Tribe is significant, representing most of the Kuki population. Per the Presidential Order, the Thadou Tribe falls under the list, representing most of the Kuki population. The recognition of the Kuki Tribe as a Scheduled Tribe, with its 37 distinct sub-tribes, underscores the diversity and complexity of the tribal landscape in India's northeastern region (Zou, S. Thangboi, 2018).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, recognizing tribes as Scheduled Tribes (ST) is crucial for their development and empowerment. The Indian Constitution safeguards STs, including educational, cultural, social, economic, political, and service benefits. Manipur, a multi-ethnic state, has 33 recognized tribes, with 25 being Kuki-Chin-Mizo and eight being Naga. The Thadous are the largest Kuki population, and the Tangkhul are the second-largest tribe. The Constitutional ST Orders and amendments have played a significant role in recognizing and categorizing these tribes. The SC and ST List Modification Order, 1956, and the SC and ST 2002 Orders, 2003 (Amendment) Act No. 10 have contributed to refining the ST list in Manipur. Recognizing "Any Kuki Tribes" and "Any Naga Tribes" as ST has also been critical in acknowledging the diversity of tribal communities in the state. Ultimately, the accurate identification of tribal people as ST is essential for ensuring their access to constitutional safeguards and promoting their overall development, which is critical for addressing the historical injustices and disparities faced by these communities.

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